

THEORETICAL BASICS OF MUSICAL CULTURE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10824082>

Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical features of music culture in preschool children.

Key words: Preschool educational organization, musical education, culture, upbringing, individual approach.

Introduction.

Forming the musical culture of preschool children in music lessons helps to develop the ability to feel, understand, love, appreciate and enjoy art phenomena.

The goal of forming children's musical culture is to convey the spiritual experience of generations expressed in musical culture in its most complete and comprehensive form, and on this basis the positive characteristics and personal characteristics of each child. To achieve this, children need constant and systematic musical training.

The task of the music director in a preschool educational institution is to introduce children to the emotional content of music, to conduct experiments in music lessons, where children learn to identify its character, conveyed feelings and mood. Also, children's perception and performance of music should be conscious. Therefore, from the first lessons, children should be taught to listen to music and think in it:

- analyze a piece of music using form
- discussions and dialogues;
- connecting the expressiveness of individual musical instruments and the expressiveness of the musical image as a whole.

In order to open the door to the world of music in front of the child, it is necessary to form his ability to successfully express himself in musical culture. Therefore, two important components of musicality should be brought up in a child: musical ear and emotional sensitivity. Without a child, it is impossible to introduce a child to this beautiful world, and the integral development of a person is also impossible.

Developing an aesthetic perception of music requires a certain system and consistency. Perception of music for preschool children is possible by choosing

appropriate works. Children are taught the simplest skills that create the first foundations of listening culture:

- the ability to listen to the work to the end;
- monitor its development;
- memorize and recognize it;
- to highlight its main idea and character, the brightest means of musical expressiveness.

In the process of listening to music, tasks of comprehensive development of the child are carried out, because his moral image is improved, his mental abilities are formed, and his physical condition is strengthened. Music helps the child not only to feel beauty, but also to create it. By regularly listening to music, children begin to distinguish and understand its means of expression, genres, composition of works, which naturally deepens aesthetic feelings.

In the process of musical work, adults form methods of mental activity in children, in this case, the ability to analyze music in a specified order (when familiarizing with expressive means):

- to determine the general essence of the expressed music by finding two or three definitions;
- analysis of means of expressiveness in a certain sequence: tempo, dynamics, register, melody, rhythm, harmony (dissonance-consonance), instruments, voices.

When listening to music, it is important to feel the mood changes expressed in the music. After drawing children's attention to the most expressive means through which these experiences are transmitted. Children will appreciate classical dance music from I. S. Bach's dance collections to F. Chopin's, F. Schubert's waltzes, P. Tchaikovsky's ballet music.

In addition to music lessons, you can use several hours of silent games, free pictures to listen to music. At the same time, it is important that children have the opportunity to listen to loud music without distracting each other.

An excellent tool for the formation of emotional sensitivity to music is children's active musical activities and, above all, singing. Musical activities include the following types of musical activities, such as choir singing, moving to music, playing children's musical instruments, listening to music, creative musical games, etc.

To teach children to sing in a choir, the music director should constantly monitor that the children sing with a soft sound attack, draw the sound, and the power of sonority is acceptable for a certain age - children sing loudly but softly

need. If possible, it is necessary to achieve all pure unison. Vocal-choir exercises are repeated from lesson to lesson with a gradual deepening of the requirements for the quality of the singing voice.

Elementary vocal-intonation skills are mastered in the course of singing activities in preschool children. Singing helps to develop and strengthen the lungs and vocal apparatus, to develop proper posture in children. By listening and performing songs, the child responds to them emotionally, perceives their artistic images, and understands the content in general. Vocal works affect emotions, create certain attitudes to things betrayed in them, develop moral qualities of a growing person.

Rhythmic education is an integral part of musical culture in kindergarten. A simple rhythm can be conveyed during movements such as clapping, simultaneous stomping, squatting, swinging from foot to foot. During the process, these dance movements use rhythmic and different songs. It is useful for children to play different music, so that while learning dance movements, they independently catch the character, rhythm and tempo of the proposed musical sample.

In musical and rhythmic activities, preschool children master various movements and their performance methods, which also require special knowledge: the nature of music and movements, musical expressive tools (tempo, dynamics, emphasis, register, pauses). Children learn the names of dance steps, learn the names of dances, round dances.

Children's creative play activities play an important role in musical education. Musical games are educational and educational in nature and can happen in different forms of musical work with children, but most often they are related to improvisation.

One of the forms of musical work that attracts children is playing musical instruments. Percussion instruments (sticks, wooden spoons, bells, triangle) are recommended for rhythmic accompaniment to the music.

One of the main tasks of listening to music is to accumulate musical experiences. Children get artistic pleasure from musical activities in kindergarten. At the same time, they learn to understand music, emphasizing the available means of musical expression.

Song improvisation is widely used in music lessons. Children's improvisational singing is based on the ability to combine, change, create new things based on the perception of music, musical hearing, imagination, existing musical and auditory experience.

Formation of children's musical culture ensures musical development based on their interdependence in various forms of musical work. At the same time, the relationship between singing, listening, playing percussion instruments, moving to music, listening and musical improvisation is realized; singing and improvisation.

Each means of forming musical culture affects others and together they serve to develop musical abilities. Listening to music educates the child's musical perception, helps him distinguish musical works. Since listening involves recognizing a piece of music, it helps children develop a musical ear and especially its emotional component.

Singing, that is, playing a melody with the voice, contributes to the active development of musical and auditory performances, develops the fretboard (a sense of tonic, correct tuning) and a sense of rhythm. The movement requires the child to coordinate the movements with the nature of the music, its pace and rhythm, that is, he should listen to the music at the same time as the movement. The same thing happens when children play musical instruments.

Thus, singing affects the success of the movement. All three main tools of musical education work in one direction - forming the musical culture of the child. The use of singing, acting and listening in music lessons is mandatory, because different forms of activity help to better master programming skills and abilities.

Conclusion.

Thus, in this final qualification work, the formation of musical culture in a preschool educational institution is considered. This topic is relevant, because introducing a child to the world of beauty should begin at preschool age. Music affects intellectual development, accelerates the growth of cells responsible for human intelligence. But mostly, music can affect a person's emotional well-being. In fact, in the modern world, real communication is often replaced by virtual communication, there are many stresses and experiences, and it is very important for a person to find a way of emotional expression for himself. Therefore, the relevance of musical education of the young generation is increasing more than ever.

To form a child's musical culture, it is necessary to develop his ability to successfully express himself in various forms of musical work - listening to music, singing, musical-rhythmic activities, musical-didactic games, children's musical instruments. Together, they nurture a child's love for music, deepen his

perception and understanding of the environment, instill a certain attitude towards him and form a musical taste.

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